

Information Retrieval Evaluation Experiments

Introduction

A lot of research on retrieval evaluation has been done over the last few decades. According to Lancaster, the first evaluation study in the field of information retrieval was likely carried out in 1953. Several attempts have been made in this direction since then. The Cranfield projects, on the other hand, were the first important studies that actually added a new dimension to retrieval system evaluation study.

The MEDLARS study and the Cranfield experiments both tried to figure out how well different indexing methods performed. The creation of a suitable system for retrieval evaluation, however, is the study's most important contribution. These studies also tried to determine the information retrieval systems' performance requirements. These researches highlighted the key performance determinants, such as recall, precision, fallout, etc. and these investigations also demonstrated the adverse link between recall and precision.

There are different types of retrieval evaluation experiments, they are.....

1. Cranfield test 1 and Cranfield test 2.
2. MEDLARS (Medical Literature Analysis and Retrieval System).
3. The SMART retrieval experiments.
4. The STAIRS (Storage And Information Retrieval System) project.
5. TREC Experiment.

Cranfield test 1

The Cranfield I study, directed by C. W. Cleverdon, was the first comprehensive assessment of retrieval systems conducted in Cranfield, UK. Cleverdon reported the first Cranfield study, which started in 1957.

The purpose of the project was to evaluate the performance of four indexing systems.

Main Components: -

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- An alphabetical Subject Catalogue
- UDC Classified catalogue and alphabetical chain index
- Faceted Classification and alphabetical index
- Uniterm coordinate index

System Characteristics

There were 1200 search topics and 18,000 indexed items in the investigation. The materials were selected equally from the broad field of aeronautics and the highly specialized subject of high-speed aerodynamics; half were research reports and the other half were periodical parts.

Three Selected indexers were....

1. one who had earlier indexing experience,
2. one who had expertise in the topic,
3. And one who had just graduated from library school and had neither experience nor subject background.

Each indexer was instructed to spend 2, 4, 8, 12, and 16 minutes indexing each source page five times. Thus, a set of 6000 indexed items was created from 100 source documents (100 documents x 3 indexers x 4 systems x 5 times). The system processed an overall of 18,000 (6000 x 3 phases) indexed items while each of these 6000 things was examined in three stages. In order to figure out whether the level of performance improved as system personnel's expertise increased, the test was separated into three separate sections.

Results

- A. With an overall average of 80%, the efficiency of all four approaches was demonstrated by recall ratios ranging from 60 to 90%.
- B. These recall ratios were found for the various systems:
 - 81.5% alphabetical index
 - 74% of the faceted Classification
 - UDC-76%
 - 82 % uniterm.
- C. Although there was a decline at the 8-minute level for unclear reasons, recall rose with longer indexing times. The recall ratios depending on the timings were as follows:

Time, Minutes	Recall %
2	73
4	80
8	74
12	83
16	84

- D. While obtaining documents indexed by the three different indexers, no noticeable variations were seen. Put otherwise, the three indexers' performances did not differ significantly from one another.
- E. It was discovered that retrieval success rates on general aeronautics areas were 4-5% higher than those on high-speed aerodynamics.
- F. The third set of 6000 items had a 3-4% higher success rate than the second group.

Analysis of failures

There were 495 failures in total. These were examined and the following numbers were discovered:

- failures to ask questions 17%
- indexing errors 60%
- searches are unsuccessful. 17%
- System malfunctions 6 %

It should be mentioned that the searching (17%) and indexing (60%) steps made up 77% of the failures. Of these 77%, 55% were explained as a human mistake, with the remaining 22% occurring as a result of limited indexing time.

Importance: -

In several ways, the Cranfield I test results ran directly to the accepted assumptions about the nature of information retrieval systems. First, the test demonstrated that an indexer's experience and subject-matter background have no bearing on a system's performance. Second, it demonstrated how poorly systems that use a faceted classification strategy to arrange documents perform when compared to the alphabetical index and uniterm approach. The Cranfield 1 test was significant in two more ways. First, it determined the key elements that influence retrieval systems' performance. Secondly, it created for the first time the methods that could be used effectively to analyse information retrieval systems. The following Cranfield 1 innovations are interesting:

- Indexing durations longer than four minutes did not significantly enhance performance.
- Non-technical indexers may generate high-quality indexing.
- The systems had a 70–90% recall rate and an 8–20% precision rate.
- Recall could be lost by 3% in exchange for a 1% increase in precision.
- There was an inverse relationship between recall and precision.
- The performance of the four indexing strategies was practically the same.

Remarks

According to Vickery, the retrieval requests are the main source of criticism. There has been a claim that the tests "manufactured" questions, which were taken from the original materials, are too similar to the documents than those from real life. Another critique was that while this test determined the performance level of the indexing systems in question, it did not provide insight into the causes of these systems' failures. Actually, the second Cranfield test took these questions into account.

Cranfield test 2

The second Cranfield test was a randomized trial designed to evaluate how index language components affected retrieval system performance. The second stage of the Cranfield studies, known as Cranfield 2, began in 1963 and concluded in 1966. By changing one element while holding the others constant, this study attempted to evaluate the impact. 1400 documents were used to evaluate a total of 29 index languages created by merging various concepts. A total of 1400 reports and articles gathered from the fields of aircraft structure and high speed aerodynamics were used for the test.

Formulating Queries

A total of 200 research papers with several cited references were compiled. After citing the reference or references in their papers, each author was required to come up with a set of questions. Additionally, the authors were asked to identify any documents that may have been pertinent to the topic they had articulated but were not acknowledged in their works. The authors determined that 1961 publications were either entirely or somewhat pertinent to the 279 queries they had collected. Ultimately, 1400 documents and 221 questions were chosen for the project. The number of pertinent papers that were found by a particular search was used to determine the system's success.

Searching

Each response was broken down into separate words. After coordination, these variables were compared to the coordinated index terms. By eliminating one query term at a time, this matching was carried out at many levels of coordination in the hopes of finding a suitable document at each level. The words of the index language, which were created by combining synonyms with the original terms, were then used to replace the query and index words. Several levels of coordination conducted searches to discover what further documents may be found. All of the index languages (described in the preceding section) were used in similar searches. For every search, a log of hits and false drops was kept.

Results: -

The collection of 1400 documents were subjected to a total of 221 questions. The average recall and precision ratios have been obtained by adding up the outcomes of every search in every language. The following factors were used to define recall and precision ratios for a certain index language: -

Level	7	6+	5+	4+	3+	2+	1+
Total hits	12	25	49	88	132	162	189
Total false drops	11	56	251	1039	3979	9811	34,127
Recall Ratio	6	13	25	44	67	82	96
Precision Ratio	52	31	16	8	3	2	1

Cranfield 2 test findings were surprising since the top-performing index languages were made up of uncontrolled single words that appeared in documents. Still, there were issues with the study's variables. Different word or phrase units, or combinations of the two, made up each index language. The questions and documents were created in the same manner. As a result, matching questions to documents would assess how effective the various specialty languages are. According to Vickery, the metrics employed in the second Cranfield study fall short in describing the operationally significant features of retrieval performance.

MEDLARS (Medical Literature Analysis and Retrieval System)

Between August 1966 and July 1967, the US National Library of Medicine's Medical Literature Analysis and Retrieval System (MEDLARS) performance was investigated. One MeSH, a thesaurus of medical subject headings, provided index entries for the test, which was performed on the operational database of MEDLARS, a database containing scientific papers. The MEDLARS test's goal was to assess the current system to identify areas for development. Around 700,000 items made up the document collection that was visible on the MEDLARS service at the time of the test.

Techniques

302 search requests were made by the user group that was chosen. The system operator formed each question in terms of MeSH and carried out searches. Following the conclusion of a search, users were supplied the sample output for evaluation of its relevance. For this review, hardcopy of the articles were provided instead of just the references. Each object that was retrieved was to be marked by the user using the following scale:

Major values are represented by H1, minor values by H2, no values by W1, and uncertain values by W2. The following formula was then used to determine the searches' precision.

$$\text{Precision Ratio} = \frac{H1+H2}{L} * 100$$

where L represents the quantity of sample items that were received. Recall was calculated using the total number of items found by this search, which was determined to be the total number of relevant items obtainable in the collection for the specified query (i.e. $100(H1+H2)/L$, where / is the total number of relevant items).

Result

The average total recall ratio was 57.7%, and the average accuracy ratio was 50.4%, when the recall and precision numbers for each of the 302 queries were combined. 3038 precision failures and 797 recall failures were recorded all through the 302 searches. As shown in the table, the primary system components were held accountable for the failures.

System attribute/Component	Recall Failures (%)	Precision Failures (%)
Index language	81(10.2)	1094(36)
Indexing	298(37.4)	393(12.4)
Searching	279(35)	983(32.4)
User-system Interaction	99(25)	503(16.6)
Others	11(1.4)	78(2.5)

The SMART Retrieval experiments

In 1964, the SMART system emerged initially as an experimental instrument to evaluate the efficacy of various analysis and search procedures. & Salton uses the next phases of the system's operation to describe it.

It works to:

- retrieve documents and to look up English-language search terms.
- conduct a written analysis that is totally computerized.
- align the contents of documents with the evaluated keyword phrases.
- obtain the stored items that most closely match the requests.

Several techniques were used to automatically analyze the content of documents, including:

- Strategies for word suffix cut-off.
- Procedures for thesaurus searching
- Approaches for developing words
- relationships between statistical phrases
- expansion of hierarchical phrases, etc.

Ways of Evaluation

- A graph of recall and precision that shows the average accuracy value at 10 unique recall points, spanning 0.1 to 1.0 at intervals of 0.1.
- Normalized recall and normalized precision are two global statistics that jointly describe the system's overall performance level.
- two shortened global statistics, known as log precision and rank recall, respectively.

Methodology

A total of 131,500 words from 1268 library science abstracts, mostly from American documenting journals distributed between 1963 and 1964, were utilized in an experiment. Eight library science experts (either librarians or students) were requested to come up with 48 search terms, each of whom provided six possible search terms for a library science student. The questions were designed to correspond with realistic information needs and have an answer in English that was grammatically correct and easy to understand. After transmission of the questions, each participant evaluated the 1268 document abstracts' validity to their six questions. If a document clearly indicated or implied from the summary that it included information linked to the query, it became relevant.

The query authors made the initial set of relevance judgments, referred to as "A judgments." Each participant completed a second set of "B judgments" for six more questions from various people in order to guarantee independence. The relevance criteria were the same for both sets. To maintain confidentiality and impartiality in the evaluation process, the "B judges" were not made aware of the "A judgments" and were not permitted to have discussions with the original evaluators.

As a result, four distinct document sets were made available for each of the 48 questions. These sets included the following things, each of which was considered significant by a separate group of people:

- A set-relevance established by the author of the question
- B set-relevance evaluated by a separate subject matter expert
- C set-relevance indicated by either assessor A or B
- Both the A and B evaluators mentioned the D set-relevance.

Three artificial language analysis processes are part of the SMART system:

1. Word form
2. Word stem
3. Thesaurus

Result

Focusing on simply contrasting recall and precision numbers, the ranking of recall-precision curves was used to assess performance for different processing techniques. The approaches were evaluated similarly by all four sets of relevant evaluations (A, B, C, and D). The word stemmed or vocabulary approaches have been demonstrated to be more effective than the word-form process, with the thesaurus topping the word stem by a little margin. The D decisions, which mirrored the consensus of the A and B judges, produced the best recall and precision outcomes. The precision for D was almost 20% greater than that of A, B, or C for low recall.

The STAIRS (Storage And Information Retrieval System) project

A report on a large-scale experiment to evaluate the retrieval efficacy of a full-text search and retrieval system was published in 1985 by Blair and Maron¹². STAIRS (Storage And Information Retrieval System) is the name of this research.

Methodology

A database of around 40,000 documents—roughly 350,000 pages of hard-copy text used in the defence of a business dispute was examined by the STAIRS study. The full-text material was accessible via the internet and could be found using specific terms, either alone or in combination with Boolean operators. Users can now refine their searches using longer, more particular, or related phrases thanks to the system's integration of the Thesaurus Linguistic System (TLS). Obtaining at least 75% of all pertinent documents for a particular request was a crucial requirement. The study's main goal was to use recall and precision metrics to assess how well the system retrieved all and just the right documents.

Two legal professionals who were familiar with STAIRS converted the 51 universal requests that the lawyers had generated into formal queries. Searches were done by legal assistants, and the lawyers received the documents they discovered for review. The records were separated into four different groups by the lawyers: "vital," "satisfactory," "marginally relevant," and "irrelevant." After making changes to the requests, the lawyers performed more investigations until they were satisfied that at least 75% of the "vital," "satisfactory," and "marginally relevant" papers had been found. The precision has been calculated by dividing the total number of recovered documents by the percentage of pertinent documents (vital, acceptable and moderately relevant). Lawyers assessed random subsets to ascertain the overall quantity of appropriate paperwork in the database in order to estimate recall through a method of sampling.

Result

The precision and recall values were computed for 40 of the 51 requests, while the remaining 11 were utilized to evaluate the sampling methods and account for possible differences in the review of the data obtained and experimental tests. In percentage terms, the precision values ranged from 100% to at least 19.6%, with an overall mean of 79% (standard deviation 23.2%). With an average of 20% (standard deviation = 15.9%), the recall values varied from a maximum of 78.7% to a minimum of 2.8%. According to these findings, just 20% of the collection's relevant papers could be retrieved, but on average, 79 out of 100 documents recovered were important. Calculating the recall and precision numbers for each of the 40 queries indicated that, in almost half of the cases, recall was 20% or less and precision was above 80%.

Blair and Maron¹² point out it is impossible for users to anticipate the exact words, mixtures, and terms used in all or most of the relevant documents, and only in those records, which is why STAIRS was only able to retrieve a maximum of five important documents in response to a request. The 'output overload'—the vast number of the database—is occasionally mentioned as one of the explanations of poor recall. They point out that it is difficult for the user to explore a collection of several thousand documents that have been obtained. In these situations, the user usually wishes to modify the question by adding increasing numbers of keywords in order to keep the output size within a functional range. However, the value of recall decreases as the output size decreases by adding overlapping words because it is possible that some important details will be left out by using redesigned queries.

TREC Experiment

With the beginning of the TREC (Text Retrieval Conference) series of studies, data extraction and measurement research witnessed a significant increase. Since its creation in 1991, TREC has welcomed researchers researching information retrieval from all over the world who focused on the development and assessment of various kinds of systems for retrieving data. Over the years, the TREC investigators have developed various innovative methods for evaluating information retrieval systems, even though its TREC series of trials significantly borrows from earlier evaluation tests. This chapter summarizes four significant yet early recovery evaluation research studies before briefly discussing the different TREC experiments.

The TREC series generated other tracks along with the ad hoc and filtering jobs. A track serves as a breeding ground for novel study topics. On average, the initial run of a track specifies the challenge and builds the infrastructure required to conduct studies regarding the specific assignment, such as test sets and evaluation techniques. Voorhees provides a table listing every TREC track, as well as the total number of research teams that took part in each track, as seen in Table.

Track	1992	1993	1994	1995	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	2002
Ad hoc	18	24	26	23	28	31	42	41	-	-	-
Routing	16	25	25	15	16	21	-	-	-	-	-
Interactive	-	-	3	11	2	9	8	7	6	6	6
Spanish	-	-	4	10	7	-	-	-	-	-	-
Confusion	-	-	-	4	5	-	-	-	-	-	-
Database merging	-	-	-	3	3	-	-	-	-	-	-
Filtering	-	-	-	4	7	10	12	14	15	19	21
Chinese	-	-	-	-	9	12	-	-	-	-	-
NLP	-	-	-	-	4	2	-	-	-	-	-
Speech	-	-	-	-	-	13	10	10	3	-	-
Cross-language	-	-	-	-	-	13	9	13	16	10	9

High Precision	-	-	-	-	-	5	4	-	-	-	-
Very large corpus	-	-	-	-	-	-	7	6	-	-	-
Query	-	-					2	5	6	-	-
Question answering	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	20	28	36	34
Web	-	-						17	23	30	23
Video	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	12	19
Novelty	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		13

There are several types of TREC Experiments. They are.....

TREC 1

Jointly sponsored by DARPA and NIST, the first Text Retrieval Meeting (TREC-1) took place at NIST in November 1992. In order to assess their information retrieval systems on the TIPSTER collection, a sizable test dataset, it brought together 28 research groups from academia and industry. Many groups had never used such a huge dataset before, demanding a major scaling of their methods. TREC-1 was innovative because it made it possible to compare systems on the same data using several evaluation techniques, promoting teamwork and creativity. The meeting established a standard for next comprehensive studies and sparked a lot of interest in the knowledge retrieval field.

According to Harman, the TREC-1 trials' initial results showed the following information.

- It appears that automatically creating questions using natural language question statements is effective.
- Natural language processing strategies were neither superior nor inferior to vector or statistical strategies; the most effective of all methods were roughly comparable.

A number of additional conclusions were also drawn from the data;

- all 24 groups that produced useful results, with one exception, performed at roughly the same level.
- The precision-recall curves barely differed.

- Despite some apparent differences in the trial designs, the same performance levels were attained. The computer platforms used ranged from PCs to powerful computers, and while the precision-recall results were similar, there was a significant scatter in the actual documents retrieved. For instance, some groups created queries consequently from the topic statements, while others produced the search queries manually; many systems failed to include relevance feedback.

TREC 2

With three types of involvement—full participation (A), limited participation using a reduced dataset (B), and evaluation-only (C) for preserving intellectual algorithms—TREC-2, which took place in August 1993, increased participation to 31 groups (22 from TREC-1 and 9 new ones). Ad hoc queries, which are common library searches, and routing queries, that utilize profile-based filtering, were the two retrieval types that were examined. New developments during the conference included larger databases (1GB to 3GB), relevance feedback, and a rise in the amount of paperwork return limitation (200 to 1,000 per topic). With significant speed gains over TREC-1, especially in routing tasks, TREC-2 showed a variety of methods for extracting text from huge collections. The potential of interfaces based on natural language has been proven by the availability of large amounts of training data, which allowed for creative experimentation and automatic query manufacturing that was on par with or better than human techniques.

TREC-3 to TREC-5

In terms of subjects and assignments, the TREC series saw substantial change. In order to explore worries with very brief user inquiries, TREC-4 further decreased subject length to about ten phrases, whereas TREC-3 provided shorter topics by eliminating some keywords. Both short and lengthy subjects were covered in TREC-5, enabling a more thorough examination of strategies appropriate for varying query lengths. These changes were made in an effort to investigate how query length affects retrieval efficiency and to encourage creative subject expansion techniques.

Additionally, specialist tracks were added to TREC-4 and TREC-5, diversifying the initial ad hoc and routing responsibilities. These programs gave academics the opportunity to investigate particular retrieval issues, like interacting with collections that are not in English (like Spanish) and creating interactive queries across several databases. Modifications of the fundamental routing and ad hoc procedures were added as specialized tracks as the TREC exercises matured. Among the tracks in TREC-4 and TREC-5 were:

- Multiple database Merging
- confusion
- AD-Hoc information Retrieval on non-English languages
- interactive usage
- Filtering

TREC-6

Three additional sections were added to TREC-6: speech, cross-language, and high-precision information retrieval. Facilitating research on systems that can retrieve pertinent documents regardless of the language of the source documents is the aim of the cross-language retrieval of information track. The goal of voice, or spoken word document recovery track, is to encourage research into methods for retrieving spoken documents, such as radio broadcasts and speeches. The highly accurate track was created to handle circumstances in which an automated retrieval user is required to obtain ten files that respond to a specific information request in five minutes.

TREC-7

TREC-7 included seven tracks besides the primary ad hoc job, two of which were novel: the query track and the very big corpus track. Building a sizable query collection was the aim of the query track. The purpose of the question loop was to generate a vast array of distinct questions for the TREC subject set, which consists of topics 1 through 50. To investigate how well retrieval techniques scale to huge document collections, the very large sample track employed a 100 GB document collection.

TREC-8 to TREC-12

The web record and answering questions (QA) tracks became available in TREC-8. While the online track investigated the suitability of conventional retrieval methods for web-based information retrieval, the QA track concentrated on giving precise responses to queries involving natural language rather than delivering whole documents. To further the study of content-based digital video retrieval, TREC-10 added a video track while TREC-9 kept seven tracks.

To assess systems' capacity to find new and pertinent information in ranking document sets, TREC-11 added a novelty track. The genome track, which focuses on genomics studies, the robust retrieval track, which aims to improve retrieval algorithms that perform poorly, and the HARD track, which emphasizes tailored queries using search environment and user interaction data, were the three new tracks added to TREC-12 in 2003.

Advantages of TREC experiments

Researchers from all around the world have come together to tackle important information retrieval problems through the TREC series. TREC's initial goal was to create significant test collections containing documents, queries, and significance criteria; however, it has yielded unexpected results. Results from ad hoc tasks and tracks are described in detail in TREC reports and overviews on the organization's website (<http://trec.nist.gov>). In order to address new issues, TREC has evolved by adding new tracks. Journals such as Information Processing and Management, Journal of the American Association for Information Sciences and Technology, and Journal of Documentation also frequently publish details regarding TREC trials.

The TREC collection of experiments has examined a variety of information retrieval techniques, including:

- Boolean retrieval
- Strategies for term weighting and statistical and probabilistic indexing
- recovery of a paragraph or sentence
- integrating the findings from multiple searches
- retrieval according to earlier evaluations of relevance
- Phrase indexing using both statistical and natural language methods
- Both query compression and query expansion
- searching using strings and concepts
- dictionary-based stemming
- answering questions
- multimedia retrieval based on content, etc.

Conclusion

By offering a methodical framework for evaluating retrieval methods and systems, information retrieval evaluation studies, like those carried out in TREC and STAIRS, have greatly improved the area. These tests indicate the significance of accuracy, memory, relevance assessments, and flexibility in responding to different kinds of queries and data volumes. To meet changing retrieval difficulties including web search, video retrieval, responding to questions, and customized searches, initiatives like TREC developed standardized test sets and novel tracks. The results highlight the importance of carefully thought-out evaluation techniques, such as relevance assessments and experimental modifications, in enhancing retrieval performance. Additionally, experiments have demonstrated how technologies such as robust retrieval methods, language processing algorithms, and thesauri can improve outcomes.

Reference

- Information Processing and Management, Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology, and Journal of Documentation. Additionally, detailed reports and findings can be explored on the TREC website (<http://trec.nist.gov>). These evaluations have laid a foundation for future advancements in information retrieval and continue to inspire research worldwide.
- Chowdhury, G.G. (2010). Introduction to Modern Information Retrieval (3rd ed.). London: Facet publishing.
- <https://www.egyankosh.ac.in/bitstream/123456789/76420/1/Unit-5.pdf>
- TREC: Experiment and Evaluation in Information Retrieval. Retrieved from <https://aclanthology.org/J06-4008.pdf>
- Ellen M. Voorhees. (n.d.). TREC: Improving information access through evaluation. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1002/bult.2003.1720320105>
- The SMART information retrieval project. Retrieved from <https://DOI:10.3115/1075671.1075771>
- STAIRS Redux: Thoughts on the STAIRS Evaluation, Ten Years after. Retrieved from <https://yunus.hacettepe.edu.tr/~tonta/courses/spring 2008/bby 703/Blair.pdf>
- Retrieved from <https://trec.nist.gov/>
- The Information Retrieval Experiment Platform. Retrieved from <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2305.18932v1>
- Recent Developments in the Evaluation of Information Retrieval Systems: Moving Towards Diversity and Practical Relevance. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/220166136>
- SMART Information Retrieval System. Retrieved from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/SMART_Information_Retrieval_System
- Cranfield experiments. Retrieved from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cranfield_experiments

- <https://ebooks.inflibnet.ac.in/lisp7/chapter/evaluation-and-measurement-of-information-retrieval-system/>
- <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/The-Cranfield-tests-Jones/5f321ab884bd97d58784dd1f6b08f054ec256d57>
- <https://trec.nist.gov/data/interactive.html>